

S-JAFFE = JAFFE: A Note on Dataset Rebranding and Misattribution

Michael J. Lyons

Ritsumeikan University

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Abstract

This note clarifies that the entity referred to in parts of the label-distribution-learning (LDL) literature as S-JAFFE is not distinct from JAFFE, the Japanese Female Facial Expression dataset. It does not introduce substantively new images or new primary annotations beyond those already contained in the original JAFFE resource; rather, it is a task-specific reformulation of JAFFE based on information already present in the original dataset (Geng, 2016; Lyons et al., 1998). We argue that use of the label S-JAFFE has contributed to citation drift and scholarly misattribution by encouraging later authors to treat a derived representation as a distinct dataset (for example, Xu et al., 2019). To reduce further credit displacement, future work should discontinue the label S-JAFFE, refer instead to JAFFE, and cite the original JAFFE dataset according to the dataset terms of use.

Keywords: JAFFE, dataset rebranding, citation drift, scholarly attribution, label distribution learning

Introduction

Dataset names are not merely descriptive labels. In benchmark-driven research, they also organize attribution, citation, and historical memory. Once a dataset name begins circulating as a citable object, credit can accumulate around that name independently of the underlying resource from which it derives. For that reason, relabeling an existing dataset is not a trivial matter. In parts of the label-distribution-learning literature, the term S-JAFFE¹ (scored JAFFE) has been used as though it denotes a distinct facial-expression dataset. This terminology is misleading. The underlying images and semantic ratings originate in JAFFE, a resource created well before the rise of label-distribution learning as a formal machine-learning paradigm (Lyons et al., 1998; Geng, 2016).

S-JAFFE is not a distinct dataset

JAFFE already contains the images and multiple expression label rating data that later made it attractive for soft-label and label-distribution-learning work. What later papers call S-JAFFE does not add a new image corpus or a new round of primary annotation. Nothing has been added to JAFFE that would justify treating the result as a distinct dataset. Rather, it re-

¹ Regarding this name, Geng wrote: "...the dataset SJAFFE (Scored JAFFE) used in this paper keeps all the scores and normalizes them into a label distribution over all the 6 emotion labels" (Geng, 2016). The scores, however, originate in JAFFE itself.

expresses information already present in JAFFE in a form suitable for a particular learning framework. As Geng (2016) puts it, S-JAFFE means “Scored JAFFE,” not a distinct dataset but a relabeling of JAFFE’s existing score structure. In practical terms, the shift is one of task formulation and representation, not one of dataset authorship.

Why this matters

The issue is not only taxonomic. Once a derived representation begins circulating under a new name, it can become a new citation node. Later authors may then cite papers using S-JAFFE without citing the original JAFFE publication or may describe S-JAFFE as though it were a distinct resource (for example, see Xu et al., 2019). The result is citation drift: credit that properly belongs to the creators of the original dataset is partially displaced toward later papers whose contribution lay chiefly in reframing, preprocessing, or relabeling the same underlying material. This is especially problematic in fast-moving machine-learning subfields, where benchmark names are repeated widely, and provenance is often compressed to a citation shortcut. An additional problem is that this reformulated version of JAFFE has been re-distributed contrary to the explicit dataset terms of use, which permit distribution only from the official Zenodo repository (Lyons, Kamachi, & Gyoba, 1997).

Derived representations should not be rebranded as datasets

There is nothing inappropriate about using JAFFE in a label-distribution-learning context, or about deriving soft-label targets from JAFFE's original semantic ratings. The difficulty arises only when such a formulation is repackaged and then presented with a new dataset name that implies novelty at the level of data creation. A more accurate description is straightforward: this is JAFFE used in a label-distribution-learning setting, or label-distribution targets derived from JAFFE. Such wording preserves methodological clarity while maintaining proper attribution. By contrast, the name S-JAFFE implies novelty, obscures provenance, and encourages the secondary literature to cite the article that rebranded the data rather than the original dataset publication.

Recommendations

To prevent further confusion and credit displacement, four corrections are advisable. First, the nomenclature S-JAFFE should be discontinued in future publications. Second, authors using these data should refer to the resource as JAFFE. Third, when a study employs soft-label, label-distribution, or otherwise reformulated targets derived from JAFFE, this should be stated explicitly as derived from JAFFE rather than as a distinct dataset. Fourth, authors should cite the original JAFFE dataset in accordance with the terms stated at the official Zenodo distribution (Lyons, Kamachi, & Gyoba, 1997). These recommendations do not inhibit methodological innovation; they simply restore transparency concerning the source of the data and the locus of the original scholarly contribution.

Conclusion

The central point of this note is straightforward: S-JAFFE = JAFFE. The former is not a distinct dataset, but a task-specific reformulation of the latter. Continued use of the rebranded label risks perpetuating citation drift and scholarly misattribution. Clearer naming and citation of the original JAFFE work according to the terms of use would better serve both the integrity of the literature and the fair allocation of credit.

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